

"Yor-Yor" in Uzbek And Karakalpak Languages Etymological Characteristics of "Haujar"

Nilufar Urazimbetova is the daughter of Abat

3rd year student of Karakalpak State University named after Berdak

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Abstract: This article talks about the common aspects of Karakalpak and Uzbek folklore. Despite the fact that the Karakalpak and Uzbek peoples belong to the group of Turkic peoples, there are many differences in their customs.

Keywords: folklore, tradition, Turkish people, song, wedding, handover, bride.

Mother alla is one of the most prominent cases of folklore. "Lullabies" is a lullaby that is absorbed into the child's psyche along with mother's milk. A mother's love for her child, good intentions and positive wishes for her future, life path, with the help of deeply meaningful words, are expressed from the heart of a mother. Lullabies consists of verses that are sung while putting the baby to sleep, and they are the most precious feelings for a person.[6:275].

Samples of folklore works are used during rituals held on sad and happy days of the people. Some of them are sung to the tune of musical instruments, and some of them sound beautiful and impressive even if they are performed musically by the performer's own voice. Since ancient times, Turkic peoples could not live without music. From the birth of a child to his death, and even when he dies of old age, he is remembered with melodious laments and dirges.

Lyrical songs, like other genres of folklore, have their own history. For example, if we analyze the song "Yor-Yor", which is popular today, we know that it appeared a long time ago. In particular, Alisher Navoi notes that "Yor-yor" was sung at the wedding of Iskandar and Ravshanak in "Saddi Iskandariy", the last epic of "Khamsa":

Qaysi chaman soridin keldi sabo yor-yor,

Ki damidin tushti o't jonim aro yor-yor.[1;34]

From this we can know that yor-yor is a work that appeared in very ancient history. The yor-yor performer, who had the talent of poetry, used to weave new quatrains depending on the wedding situation. [4;145] The song "Yor-yor" of the Uzbek people is compared with the song "Haujar" in Karakalpak folklore. "Haujar" is a song about the transfer of a girl. "Haujar" was said by the girl when she was being carried out of her house. The young men and women next to him sang along to the refrain of the song. "Haujar" is based on the motif of farewell. But in the song of Hajar, not only the girl's feelings of farewell are given, but also her dissatisfaction with her fate and regretful experiences are given. This is due to the fact that in the past, in the clan-patriarchal system, girls did not have freedom of choice, they were passed on against her will. That is why girls' mood of protest was more in Hajar songs.

[5;11] "Haujar" and "Yor-Yor" originated in Turkic peoples. Later, the "j"-speaking layer of the Turks will be called "Haujar", and the "y"-speaking layer will be called "Yor-yor". This is how "Haujar" originally came about. We notice that the meaning of the words in it is the lament of a girl who is losing her home and parents.

Óz akemniń esigi, jupar esik háujar,
 Kirsem ,shiqsam shashimdi siypar esik háujar,
 Qayin atamniń esigi sheńgel esik háujar
 Kirsem, shiqsam shashimdi jular esik háujar.
 Qoy súyedi balasin qozim-aw dep, háujar,
 Hesh nárseni kórmegen bozim-aw, dep háujar.
 Uzatqanda qiz jilap, óksip-óksip,háujar,
 Qáne meniń qizdađı nazim-ay dep ,háujar.
 Torđay súyer balasin, tolđanim dep, háujar
 Tobilđiniń basinda qonđanim dep, háujar,
 Uzatqanda qiz jilar óksip-óksip, háujar,
 Sonda meniń qurayday, solđanim dep, háujar.

According to the content of the song, the girl is expressing her anguish in her heart. Along with the fact that the girl is leaving for the person she doesn't love, it shows that she is struggling to think about her value by raising her understanding. [2;15] That is, he lives in his parents' arms, playing, laughing and caressing, the door of his house caresses his hair like silk, and now he is going home, he is suffering in this house, it is a thorn like the door of that house. he complains about pulling his hair. The girl sang the song while crying and hugging her parents.

But in the next 70s and 80s, háujar became a different type and was performed by famous artists at weddings. The song "Yor-yor" belonging to Uzbek folklore has been used in the current form of "Haujar" since ancient times. That is, the song was performed not by the girl, but by other women. The meaning of "Yor-yor" is also meant to be said by others:

Hay-hay o'lan, jon o'lan
 O'lanchi qiz, yor-yora o'lanchi qiz.
 Va'dasida turmagan, yolg'onchi qiz
 Yor-yor-ey yolg'onchi qiz.
 Tog'da toychoq kishnaydi-ey
 Ot bo'ldim, deb
 Uyda kelin yig'laydi-ey
 Yot bo'ldim, deb.
 Yig'lama qiz, yig'lama yo
 To'y saniki, yor-yor,
 Ostonasi tillodan-ey,uy saniki
 Yor-yorey uy saniki.

In Yor-Yorar, they sing a lot about the bride. These praises and wishes apply to the present

bride, her grandmother who was once a bride, and her granddaughter who will be a bride in the future. [3;192]

Uzoqqa borgan qizning

Rangi sariq, yor-yor,

Ko'zidan oqqan yoshi

Misli ariq yor-yor.

Tokchadagi qaychini

Zang bosibdi yor-yor,

Yangi tushgan kelinni

The main difference between the two songs is that "Yor-yor" is intended to be sung by a foreigner, and "Haujar" is intended to be sung by the girl, that is, the bride. In the Uzbek and Karakalpak peoples, from time immemorial, special attention has been paid to the health of the child, not only physically, but also mentally and spiritually. For this reason, the ancestors knew that in the formation of a healthy and pure mind of a child, the reciting of Lullabies in the crib plays an important role.[7:685]

To conclude, the Uzbek and Karakalpak peoples are etymologically the same people. The psychological experience of the mother who sang lullabies to the baby can be seen in the words of this lullabies. Despite the fact that their customs today have some differences, they are the same in origin and have undergone some changes over the centuries.

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